

**SHOULD THE OLD TESTAMENT BE USED IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
CHRISTIAN ETHICS?**

By

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All Scripture is breathed out by God and profitable for teaching, for reproof, for correction, and training in righteousness (2 Tim 3:16, ESV). Therefore, the Old Testament should be used for the development of Christian ethics. The New Testament did not elaborate on certain moral, civil, and social ethics. On the other hand, God extensively spoke to his people through his messengers and revealed his moral character and his demands for moral righteousness and justice in the Old Testament (Lev 21:8, Isa 1:17). However, one should exercise caution in drawing from moral, social, and civil principles. The context, culture, and purpose of the Old Testament are different from the current secular context. If we exercise caution in understanding the contextual difference, we can draw the legitimate principles from treasures of the Old Testament and apply them to our day-to-day lives. We can suggest those principles to the larger culture around us.

First, we need to understand the worldview of Israelites in order to understand the relationship of Israelites with God and their social, cultural, and civil values. Christopher J. H. Wright emphasized that theology and ethics are inseparable, and it is difficult to alienate the values and ethics of Israelites from their faith and beliefs about God. Wright explained the worldview of Israelites as follows: God has created the world and he is the owner of it, humans are made in the image of God, humans rebelled against God and brought disruptions in the relationships, God has a plan of redemption which begins from Abraham, father of Israel and then to all the nations. Wright pointed out the three pillars of Israel's worldview: God

(theological angle), Israel (social angle), and the land (economic angle).¹ To Israel, God is one and there is no else beside him. His acts revealed him and his character as true God. When Israelites served other gods and worshipped, it was counted as an ethical sin apart from religious sin. God acted in the history of Israel to bring redemption, make a covenant, and build his relationship with them.² Israelites are bound to obey God's revealed will in his Word and align themselves to God's social, civil, and political ethical norms.³ The social structure of Israel is unique in that YHWH is their ultimate king and it is God who owns the land and distributes it to people and demands justice. All aspects of life including land ownership, sexuality, fertility, marriage, social, and religious affairs are under the authority of God.⁴

Second, we should understand the content of Old Testament ethics and its limitations before we apply it to Christians. Holiness is supremely important in all areas of life for Israelites because their God is holy (Lev 11:45). The moral nature, character, and commands of Yahweh are the ground for the Old Testament ethics. The call for holiness separates them from other nations. Contemporary biblical ethicists believe that holiness is one of the forming fundamental themes of Old Testament ethics.⁵ Holiness in the family and society is important. Marriage was instituted by God, he ordained the union of male and female to bear the children and subdue the earth. God established the norm of human family life (Gen 2:4). Marriage is a covenant act made before God and society. Children are expected to honor their parents.⁶ Old Testament ethics

¹ Christopher J. H. Wright, *Old Testament Ethics for the People of God* (Downers Grove, Illinois: InterVarsity Press, 2004) 17-19.

² Wright, *Old Testament Ethics for the People of God*, 24-25.

³ Wright, *Old Testament Ethics for the People of God*, 30-31.

⁴ Wright, *Old Testament Ethics for the People of God*, 67-68.

⁵ Walter C. Kaiser, *Toward Old Testament Ethics* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 1983), 139-141.

⁶ Kaiser, *Toward Old Testament Ethics*, 154-155.

include the foundations, governing principles, and laws for social ethics and justice. Humans are inherently worthy of dignity and respect as they are made in the image of God (Gen 1:26-27). It is a deliberate sin and violation of law to murder a human (Ex 20:13). It is a sin to harden the heart against a poor brother (Deut 15:7-11). God rebuked injustice and acts of mistreatment and taking fraudulent advantage of poor. God's people are expected to give heed to widows and orphans.⁷

Third, in spite of the extensive rich treasures of ethics in the Old Testament, there are some limitations. The Old Testament law is primarily given to Israelites only (Deut 23:3). In that sense, there is a nationalistic limitation. The historical contextual limitations prevented people from obeying the standards of the law. God did not deliberately condemn slavery, polygamy, and low views of women when it was reported in the Old Testament due to the historical limitations. There is a legalistic limitation to apply the law because humans are imperfect in obeying the law. The materialistic limitation of the law is true because the law itself did not compartmentalize the spiritual and material life. However, the spiritual aspect of the law is evident when one understands the nature of God, his holy commandments, and his ordinances for family, social, and political life.⁸

Fourth, the ethics of the Old Testament are extremely resourceful and valuable when one correctly applies them. Protestants applied the law for three basic purposes: social use, convictional use, and normative use. The law acts as a restraint against human sin and social evil. The law convicts human sin by reflecting on God's standards and his expectations for his image-bearers. It acts as a lamp to the feet in guiding and training people in moral righteousness. There are three approaches in applying all the law: discontinuity, continuity, and

⁷ Kaiser, *Toward Old Testament Ethics*, 159-161.

⁸ Kaiser, *Toward Old Testament Ethics*, 34-37.

semi-continuity.⁹ I hold that there is a discontinuity in the sense that certain laws like ceremonial and civil laws are not applicable to us. Since the Old Covenant is not operative after the coming of Christ, Christians are not bound to the old covenant in a legalistic sense. However, we live in a new covenant age,¹⁰ and we are expected to obey our Lord. On the other hand, the basic ethical and moral principles behind all the laws are still applicable. Calvin and Luther believed that there are moral norms found in the Old Testament and they are useful for the instruction and development of Christian ethics.¹¹ At last, when we preach and teach the laws, we should not teach them apart from the New Testament. We should always preach ethics in the light of the gospel of Jesus Christ. We respond to God's grace in obedience after being saved by God's grace in salvation.¹²

⁹ David W. Jones, *An Introduction to Biblical Ethics*. ed. Daniel R Heimbach (Nashville, TN: B&H Academic, 2013), 78-79.

¹⁰ Thomas R. Schreiner, *40 Questions About Christians and Biblical Law* (Grand Rapids, MI: Kregel Publications, 2010), 71.

¹¹ Schreiner, *40 Questions About Christians and Biblical Law*, 99.

¹² Schreiner, *40 Questions About Christians and Biblical Law*, 229.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Jones, David W. *An Introduction to Biblical Ethics*. Edited by Daniel R Heimbach. Nashville, TN: B&H Academic, 2013.

Kaiser, Walter C. *Toward Old Testament Ethics*. Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 1983.

Schreiner, Thomas R. *40 Questions About Christians and Biblical Law*. Grand Rapids, MI: Kregel Publications, 2010.

Wright, Christopher J. H. *Old Testament Ethics for the People of God*. Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 2004.